

Discover Collectively Open Science Projects

The CRlators

A major appeal of Open Science is the capacity to harness collective intelligence and face big scientific challenges, unmet when researchers are working in isolation. Below is a list of such projects. Work your way through the list (up to you if you wish to divide and conquer, work in couples or as a group) to discover the projects. Apply your score (1-5 low-to-high score), using 10 of the Vienna Open Science Principles (Do read here: <https://viennaprinciples.org/>) to rank the projects' openness'. Add a few comments on what you appreciated and what you think could be improved in these projects.

Project	Premise of the project in one simple phrase!	Accessibility	Discoverability	Publication	Reusability	Reproducibility	Transparency	Understandability	Collaboration	Evaluation	Public Good	Total score	positive remarks	Improvement remarks
Human Brain Project	International and large scale research platform in neuroscience, computing, and brain-related medicine (and building a digital platform: https://ebrains.eu/about)	limited access	3.5	4.5	4.5	4	5	4	4	5	4.5	4.33333333		
Event Horizon Telescope												#DIV/0!		
Science Feedback	scientists collaborating to assess the scientific accuracy of news headlines and viral posts on social media (that relate to climate or health)	5	4	4	3	2	5	5	3	4	5	3.88888889		
Open Worm	OpenWorm is an open source project dedicated to creating the first virtual organism in a computer body and nervous system	5	2	4	4	3.5	3	4	4	3.5	4	3.55555556		
Safecast	Safecast is an international volunteer driven non-profit organization whose goal is to create useful, accessible, and granular environmental data. All Safecast data is published, free of charge.	4.5	4	2	4	4	2		4.5			3.41666667		
SenseBox	SenseBox is a hardware and software company that offer educational tools for programming, IoT, coding, etc. Also, for the public and	2.5	3	3	4	3	4	3	2	3	2	3		
Kiron	Ideas exchange and learning platform for students	2	4		2	0						2		